

ARDC Digital Research Skills Strategy Tool

(HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons version)

A decision support tool to determine user roles, skills proficiencies and training approaches

Adapted by Kit Greenhill from the [ARDC Digital Research Skills Strategy Tool](#)

4 June 2026

CONTENTS

About	2
Access	3
How to use	3
1. Use this tool iteratively	3
2. Prefilled examples	3
3. Create roles and personas (Tab 3)	4
4. Map ARDC Digital Research Skills Taxonomy to roles (Tab 4)	5
5. Nominate ways to help users gain required skills (Tab 4)	7
6. Repeat steps 4-5 for TaDiRAH (Tab 5) and the UK Data Service Data Skills Framework (Tab 6).	8
7. Add your own skills framework	8
Citations	9

About

This is a decision tool to help projects in the ARDC HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons determine components of a digital research skills strategy.

When you create a skills strategy, you need to work out:

- which people
- need which skills
- at what level
- delivered how.

This tool helps you:

- create typical user roles that outline groups who need distinct clusters of skills
- describe training preferences and pain points for each role
- identify which skills are needed by each role from three different skills lists
 - the [ARDC Digital Research Capabilities and Skills Framework](#)
 - [TaDiRAH: Taxonomy of Digital Research Activities in the Humanities](#)
 - [UK Data Service Data Skills Framework](#)
- nominate the level of competency each role requires
- map out the training approach for each skill.

You do not have to complete each process for the tool to be useful. You may only want to create user personas. The tool presents a set of useful skills taxonomies as a spreadsheet, which may be the only way you want to use it. You may want to insert a different skills framework or taxonomy instead of, or as well as, the ones provided. You may only want to identify relevant skills, but not levels needed.

This tool can be used by:

- research infrastructure providers to identify skills gaps in potential users, and how to approach these
- employers to conduct employee skills audits
- individuals to identify which skills they need to work on
- consortia to identify common users with common skills gaps, to create a collaborative training plan.

The Skilled Workforce Development Team of the [Australian Research Data Commons](#) developed the [ARDC Digital Research Skills Strategy](#) tool to support the ARDC mission to accelerate Australian research and innovation. The tool is an example of ARDC work to support excellence in the creation, analysis and retention of high-quality data assets. Contact us on contact@ardc.edu.au.

Access

1. Log in to a Google account.
2. Click the “Access Now” button below.
3. An online copy of the decision tool will be created as a Google Sheet in your personal drive (MyDrive).
4. It is best to work with the tool as a Google Sheet online.
5. You can download the Google Sheet as an Excel spreadsheet, but:
 - the coloured dropdown menus will display as text only, and only be visible when you click on the cell
 - you will only be able to select one option from the “Skills Approach” column in Tab 4.

Access Now

How to use

1. Use this tool iteratively

Cycle through the tabs iteratively. For example, as you identify the level of skills proficiency for each role, a new role with a distinct skills cluster may emerge as you realise that there are 2 distinct skills subgroups in the original role.

2. Prefilled examples

The tool is pre-filled with 6 example personas and skills profiles, for social sciences researchers, mapped against all skills as an example. These have a yellow background and are for illustration only.

You will create your own personas in the cells with a pale blue background, to match your own users with their own skills requirements.

3. Create roles and personas (Tab 3)

3.1 Rows 13 to 19 with a yellow background are 6 example personas – researchers working in Social Sciences, all with distinctly different skills requirements. You can delete these when you have created your personas.

Phyllida the Phd	Raj the Researcher	Stacey the Statistician	Corey the Coder	Margaret the Manager	Xenia the External
PhD pre-start A PhD student writing candidacy	Social Sciences Researcher A Social Sciences Researcher using everyday data skills in their research. Not a digital, data or statistical specialist	Social Sciences Researcher - Statistics specialist A Social Sciences Researcher who specialises in statistical methods	Social Sciences Researcher - Coding specialist A Social Sciences Researcher who codes and completes some tasks expected of a research software engineer	Social Sciences Data project manager A Social Sciences Researcher who manages a data infrastructure project	Researcher from outside Social Sciences discipline A researcher with another disciplinary background who needs to use digital social sciences skills in their research

Figure 1. Six example personas from Tab 3

3.2 Add your own personas to the blanks with a blue background. Aim for around 6.

3.3 The first persona is prefilled. It is a user with the base-level knowledge required (PhD student pre-start). This will help you articulate what skills are necessary, but assumed. What skills will all users need?

3.4 Identify 3 to 5 more roles to cover groups of people who need a distinct, separate set of knowledge and skills. These may be different to personas you have already created to divide audience sectors for communications. This is about clusters of skills needed.

3.5 How you group users to create roles will depend on the type of activity they are engaged in.

Think of the typical users you had in mind when you decided to create a skills strategy. You may choose to divide roles according to specific research tasks (e.g. a digital humanist who codes, a statistical specialist) or by university level (e.g. PhD student, mid-career researcher, Head of School) or by job description (e.g. Research Software Engineer, Parliamentary Assistant). You may divide them by relationship to data (e.g. data custodians, data stewards).

You may need to be very specific for some, less so for others. You might find yourself mixing and matching. The main thing is to identify the major sets of people with different skills needs.

Skills roles and personas					
Name		Role	Typical data task	Goals and motivations	Skills acquisition preferences
EXAMPLES - SOCIAL SCIENCES RESEARCHER PERSONAS - Delete these					
Phylida the Phd		PhD pre-start A PhD student writing candidacy	Organising citations and electronic documents for candidacy proposal	*Impressing supervisor *Getting Candidacy *May be very receptive to learning new methods and skills because not yet set on a path	*Opportunities for mentoring and forming networks, especially with peers * Basic introductory concepts revised before new concepts introduced * Contextualisation of new concepts so they can see relevance * Opportunities for hands-on learning * Can spend time on learning activities * Free or very low cost
Raj the Researcher		Social Sciences Researcher A Social Sciences Researcher using everyday data skills in their research. Not a digital, data or statistical specialist	Cleaning and preparing data for analysis	* Potential promotion * Research publication * Help research students gain skills	* As fast as possible * Timed to fit in with academic year - short, intense bursts * Self-paced learning that can be picked up during irregular space in daily schedule
Stacey the Statistician		Social Sciences Researcher - Statistics specialist A Social Sciences Researcher who specialises in statistical methods	Creating a digital twin to simulate social impact of a policy decision	* Potential promotion * Research publication * Help junior staff gain skills	* More likely to be working as part of a team, so learning from colleagues or in multi-disciplinary team training sessions * Will need high-level, expert understanding of some concepts, so material needs to be complex enough

Figure 2. Three example personas from Tab 3 showing some completed description fields

3.6 For each role, create a persona typical of that role, to help you tailor later training material and be more precise when you assign competency levels in Tab 4. The suggested fields are:

- Job title
- Sector
- Typical data task
- Goals and motivations
- Skills acquisition preferences
- Skills pain points and challenges.

4. Map ARDC Digital Research Skills Taxonomy to roles (Tab 4)

Now you have your draft set of user roles, identify the skills these roles need by mapping against the ARDC Digital Research Skills Taxonomy.

4.1 Add your own roles to the Skills/roles matrix in Tab 4.

Figure 4. Using Paste special > Transposed to copy persona descriptions from Tab 3 to Tab 4 at cell H5.

- From Tab 3, copy cells 6A to 11C (or all cells containing Name, image and Role for your personas)
- Move your cursor to Tab 4 cell H5 (USER ROLES)
- Use *Paste special* > *Transposed* to paste the roles across the top of the table.

4.2 Look at the example roles with a yellow background (Column N onwards) to see a completed skills/roles matrix. This is dummy data that should not be used for skills planning.

Skills roles mapped to the ARDC Digital Skills Taxonomy					EXAMPLES: Deeds team					
Governance - Capability family					Phylida	Raj	Stacey	Corey	Margaret	
CAPABILITY CLUSTER	CAPABILITY	SKILL FAMILY	SKILL CLUSTER	SKILL	HDR pre-start	SS Researcher	SS Researcher-statistician	SS Researcher-coder	SS Data project manager	
Digital Research Infrastructure Governance	Foundational - Research methodologies & practices	Institutional policies		Awareness	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	
				Awareness	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	
		Funder & publisher policies		Awareness	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	
				Awareness	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	
		Policies	Government policies & legislation		Awareness	Working	Working	Working	Practitioner	Practitioner
					Awareness	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner
			Data standards (generic and community-specific)		Working	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner
					Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner
		Standards	Intellectual property		Working	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner
					Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner
	Research integrity			Working	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	
				Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	
	Data governance	Contracts / Agreements	Data sharing		Working	Practitioner	Practitioner	Expert	Expert	
					Awareness	Practitioner	Practitioner	Expert	Expert	
		Data transfer		Awareness	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	
				Working	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner		
				NA	Working	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	
				NA	Working	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	
	Digital Research Infrastructure Governance	Policies	NRI strategies, roadmaps & decadal plans		NA	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner
					Awareness	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner
Access & use policies				Awareness	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	
				Awareness	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	
Risk & security policies			Awareness	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner		
			Awareness	Working	Working	Working	Working			
Lifecycle management		Design & build		NA	NA	NA	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	
				NA	Awareness	Awareness	Expert	Expert		
		Operation & maintenance		NA	Awareness	Awareness	Expert	Expert		
				NA	Practitioner	Practitioner	Working	Practitioner		
	Impact reporting		NA	Awareness	Awareness	Working	Practitioner	Practitioner		
			NA	Working	Working	Practitioner	Practitioner			
End-of-life of infrastructure		Working	Practitioner	Practitioner	Expert	Expert				
		Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner				
Security & ethics	Privacy & legal obligations		Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner			
			Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner	Practitioner			

Figure 5. The ARDC digital skills taxonomy data governance capability family mapped to required levels for example personas

4.3 Assign competency levels to all skills needed by each role.

- Consider the skill in the very last column of each row. Ignore the more general skills in the cells to the left.
- For each skill, use the drop downs to indicate the competency required for each role. For explanations see *Tab 8. "Competency indicators explained"*.
- Select from:
 - Not applicable
 - Awareness
 - Working
 - Practitioner
 - Expert

4.4 If you are unsure about the competency required by a role, and are thinking "it depends on...", consider whether this role should actually be two separate roles with a unique set of required skills.

5. Nominate ways to help users gain required skills (Tab 4)

For skills applicable to at least one role, go to the green Skills Approach column and tick in the dropdown menu one or more ways you will help your users gain this skill. Select as many as you will do for that skill. Not all roles will require each skill to the same extent, but you are recording whether there will be **any** action to support any users to gain the skill.

Select from:

- Deliver live – design and deliver live in-person or online training
- Create self-service – create online guides and training materials
- Webinar - run as an online webinar
- Refer to existing – link to other resources: skills strategy will involve locating excellent learning materials that already exist and providing links to these for users
- Assume skills – skills needed to access infrastructure, but skills strategy will not involve helping users learn these
- Not required – not needed to access infrastructure.

Skills roles mapped to the ARDC Digital Skills Taxonomy						
Unsworth, K. (2024). ARDC digital research capabilities and skills framework: The framework and its components (Versions v1 - Consultations (2021-2023)). Australian Research Data Commons. https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.14188836						
SKILLS APPROACH						
HOW WILL YOU HELP USERS GAIN THIS SKILL?						
CLUSTER	CAPABILITY	SKILL FAMILY	SKILL CLUSTER	SKILL		
Data governance	Foundational - Research methodologies & practices	Institutional policies			Assume skills	
		Funder & publisher policies			Refer to existing	
	Policies	Government policies & legislation			Assume skills	
		Data standards (generic and community-specific)			Refer to existing	
		Intellectual property			Create self service	
	Standards	Research integrity			Refer to existing	
		Data sharing			Assume skills	
		Data transfer			Assume skills	
	Contracts / Agreements	Data linkage			Assume skills	
	Digital Research Infrastructure Governance	Policies	NRI strategies, roadmaps & decadal plans			Not required
			Access & use policies			Assume skills
			Risk & security policies			Assume skills
			Technology transfer & IPR			Not required
			Initiation & planning			Create self service
		Lifecycle management	Design & build			Deliver live
Operation & maintenance					Assume skills	
Impact reporting					Assume skills	
End-of-life of infrastructure					Assume skills	
Business continuity including sustainability planning					Assume skills	
Security & ethics		Cyber security, including crisis response and disaster recovery procedures			Deliver live	
		Privacy & legal obligations			Create self service	
					Refer to existing	
					Refer to existing	
					Create self service	

Figure 6. The ARDC digital skills taxonomy data governance capability family mapped to skills approach

6. Repeat steps 4-5 for TaDiRAH (Tab 5) and the UK Data Service Data Skills Framework (Tab 6).

Example personas are not provided for these tabs.

7. Add your own skills framework

You can copy Tab 4 and replace the entire ARDC Digital Research Skills Taxonomy with just those skills you have selected. Or, you could locate another skills framework and paste this in to check which of these your personas will need, and the skills approach you may take.

Citations

Skills lists included in the tool

Unsworth, K. (2024). *ARDC digital research capabilities and skills framework: The framework and its components (Versions v1 - Consultations (2021-2023))*. Australian Research Data Commons. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.14188836>

Borek, L., Hastik, C., Khramova, V., & Geiger, J. (2021, July 22). TaDiRAH: Taxonomy of digital research activities in the Humanities. <https://vocabs.dariah.eu/tadirah/en/>

Higgins, V., Price, D., & King-Hele, S. (2024). The UK Data Service Data Skills Framework for working with large scale survey data, census, and macro-level aggregate data. UK Data Service. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11110082>

The competency indicator descriptions are from p.15 of :

Plummer, D., Kearney, S., Monagle, A., Collins, H., & Perry, V. (2021). *Skills and competency framework: Supporting the Information Management Framework and the National Digital Twin*. Digital Built Britain. https://www.cdbb.cam.ac.uk/files/010321cdbb_skills_capability_framework_vfinal.pdf

This work was adapted from the ARDC Digital Research Skills Strategy Tool

ARDC Skilled Workforce Development Team (2025). *ARDC Digital Research Skills Strategy Tool*. Australian Research Data Commons, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16892110>